

A MODEL FOR THE MODULUS REDUCTION DURING FATIGUE CYCLING OF AN INJECTION MOULDED GLASS/NYLON COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

During fatigue cycling of an injection moulded glass/nylon composite the modulus falls as a consequence of damage accumulated in both the skin and core layers. Empirical expressions are developed separately to predict the modulus reduction in the skin and core layers and these expressions are then combined in an appropriate way to predict modulus reduction/cycling curves for skin/core composite specimens with different widths. The predicted modulus reduction/cycling curves are in reasonable agreement with experimental data for a range of peak stresses and specimen widths.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The fatigue performance of continuous fibre composites has been extensively studied and models have been developed which attempt to predict the modulus reduction with fatigue cycling which occurs as a consequence of damage accumulation (for example, see (1)). However, only limited research has been concerned with the stiffness reduction of discontinuous fibre composites although early work on a range of short fibre materials has shown that damage accumulation during fatigue cycling is accompanied by a modulus reduction (e.g. 2,3,4).

The work presented here forms part of a study to investigate modulus reduction and damage accumulation during the fatigue cycling of an injection moulded glass/nylon composite and is concerned with predicting the reduction in Young's modulus with fatigue cycling. Empirical expressions, derived from testing both the as-moulded composites and skin layers machined from these composites, are combined to produce predictions of modulus reductions for skin/core composite specimens at different peak stresses and specimen widths.

2.0 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Tension-tension fatigue tests were performed on a 50% by weight long discontinuous glass fibre reinforced nylon composite having a skin/core structure originating from the injection moulding

process. Specimens, 20mm wide, were cut parallel to the flow direction using a diamond saw from 160mm square injection moulded coat hanger plaques. Tapered end tags of the same material were used to relieve stress concentrations at the grips. Prior to testing, all specimens were dried for 48 hours at 50°C under vacuum.

Fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature using a triangular waveform which was chosen to keep the rate of stress application constant throughout the cycling (further details are given in (4)). During cycling the modulus falls as a consequence of damage accumulated in both the skin and core layers. Damage in the core was quantified using a dye penetrant/sectioning technique (see (5)). The major form of damage in the core was transverse cracking which increased in density with cycling. The modulus reduction in the skin layers during cycling was measured using specimens consisting of skin alone, the core and the second skin layer having been removed by milling.

2.1 Skin Layer Modulus Reduction with Cycling

Modulus reduction/cycling curves for specimens consisting of skin alone are shown in Figure 1. At each peak stress, similar trends in modulus reduction are observed. Initially the modulus falls rapidly and the rate of modulus reduction decreases with fatigue cycling. This observation suggests that the experimental data may obey an expression of the form:

$$-\left(\frac{1}{E_s}\right) \frac{dE'_s}{dN} = \frac{\alpha}{N^\beta} \quad (1)$$

where α and β are constants and E_s, E'_s are the initial and current modulus, respectively. After some manipulation, the data is found to be reasonably well described by the empirical expression:

$$\left(1 - \frac{E'_s}{E_s}\right) = 2 \times 10^{-4} N^{\left(\frac{\sigma_s - 16}{115}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where σ_s is the peak stress (in MPa) applied to the skin layer during cycling.

The predictions of equation 2 are compared in Figures 2 with the experimental data for three peak stresses in the range 75MPa to 97MPa. For each peak stress, equation 2 predicts the correct trend in modulus reduction and there is reasonable agreement between the empirical predictions and the experimental data. It should be pointed out that the likely mechanism of damage accumulation in the skin layers is fibre/matrix debonding but this was not observed experimentally (4).

2.2 Core Layer Modulus Reduction with Cycling

During fatigue cycling of the skin/core composites, the major form of damage in the core is transverse cracking which initiates predominantly at the specimen edges and grows across the specimen width with cycling (5). These experimental observations form the basis of a semi-empirical model for the core layer modulus reduction. In this model, the cracks are idealised to be in a model array, shown schematically in Figure 3. All the cracks are imagined to initiate at the specimen edges during the first cycle of the fatigue test and each crack is taken to have the same

length, $2a$, which increases with cycling. The cracks have a constant spacing in the model which is taken to be the final average crack spacing for all specimens (about 0.9mm). Hence the damaged core consists of a cracked portion of length a which is increasing in extent, and an uncracked portion which is decreasing in extent. The modulus of the composite containing a fully cracked core can be derived with the aid of a shear-lag analysis (such an analysis was shown to be appropriate to the cracking in the core in (5)) and an effective modulus can be derived for the core as a whole which is subsequently added to the contribution from the skin layers (section 2.3). This is not a wholly satisfactory procedure, but does enable the effective modulus of the fully cracked core to be derived.

The extent of cracking in the core, which is characterised by the crack length, a , is derived from experimental data. Figure 4 shows an example of the crack length, a , plotted as a function of the number of cycles for specimens cycled at a peak stress of 70 MPa. It was found that an empirical expression could be derived which related the crack length, a , to the peak stress and the number of fatigue cycle such that:

$$a = 5 \times 10^{-6} N^{0.3} \sigma^{2.5} \quad (3)$$

In Figure 5, this function is plotted together with the experimental data. Each point represents a separate composite specimen from which the crack length was determined. There is reasonable agreement between the empirical expression and the data with results from tests at three peak stresses superimposing. The effective modulus of the core with cracks of length a is then

$$\bar{E}_c = E'_c \left(\frac{2a}{W} \right) + E_{c(0)} \left(W - \frac{2a}{W} \right) \quad (4)$$

where \bar{E}_c is the effective modulus of the partially cracked core, $E_{c(0)}$ is the longitudinal Young's modulus of the uncracked core (experimentally determined to be 4.2 GPa), and E'_c is the effective modulus of the fully cracked core. W is the specimen width, which appears explicitly in the expression for the core layer modulus, since the cracks initiate and grow from the specimen edges.

2.3 Composite Modulus Reduction Curves

In the previous sections empirical expressions have been developed separately for the modulus reduction in the skin and core layers. It is now possible to combine these expressions to predict modulus reduction/cycling curves for skin/core composite specimens.

As outlined in section 2.2, the model assumes an array of cracks in the core. The average stress carried by the skin layer depends on whether the skin surrounds cracked or uncracked core, and is, of course, higher when the skin surrounds cracked core. This gives rise to maximum and minimum values for the average stress at which the skin layers are cycled, corresponding to the no-crack and the fully-cracked situations. Upper and lower limits for the stress carried by the skin layer have therefore been considered. The effective modulus of the skin layers is given by;

$$\bar{E}_s = \frac{2a}{W} E'_s + \left(1 - \frac{2a}{W} \right) E_s \quad (5)$$

where a is calculated using equation 3 and E'_s is calculated from equation 2 using the appropriate value for the stress carried by the skin layer i.e. the upper or lower limit. \bar{E}_s is the normalised modulus of the skin layer, E'_s is the normalised modulus of the skin layers surrounding cracked core and E_s is the normalised modulus of the skin layers surrounding uncracked core.

The modulus of a skin/core composite specimen can now be calculated using a rule-of-mixtures expression for the contribution from the skin and core layers:

$$E = V_s \bar{E}_s + (1 - V_s) \bar{E}_c \tag{6}$$

where E , \bar{E}_s and \bar{E}_c are the current modulus of the composite, skin and core layers respectively. V_s is the volume fraction of skin (taken to be 0.8 on the basis of measurements made on cross-sections of the composites).

3.0 COMPARISON OF PREDICTED MODULUS REDUCTION/CYCLING CURVES WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Figure 6 shows an example of the predicted modulus reduction/cycling curves together with experimental data for composite specimens cycled at 80 MPa. In these figures the continuous lines represent the predictions (using upper and lower limits for the skin layer stresses) and the points are experimental data. The correct modulus reduction trend is predicted and reasonable agreement is obtained between the predictions and experimental data.

The empirical expressions described above were derived using experimental data obtained during fatigue tests on 20 mm wide specimens. However, the expressions contain a dependence on specimen width which arises from the development of the cracking from the edges of the composites. To check the validity of the expressions for different specimen widths, fatigue tests were performed on coupons having widths of 10 mm and 30 mm.

Figure 7 shows the experimental modulus reduction/cycling curves for composite specimens at the three specimen widths. The data shows a strong dependence of modulus reduction with specimen width, such that the normalised modulus reduction is greater at a given number of cycles for the narrower specimens.

Figure 8 show predicted modulus reduction curves together with experimental data for coupons which are 10mm and 30mm wide (again using upper and lower limits for the stress in the skin layers). For both specimen widths, there is reasonably good agreement between the predictions and the experimental data.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

1. An empirical expression has been derived for the modulus reduction with cycling of skin/core injection moulded glass/nylon composite specimens. The expression is based on observations of crack accumulation in the core and measured modulus reductions on specimens consisting of skin alone.

2. The expression for the modulus reduction with cycling contains an explicit dependence on

specimen width. Reasonable agreement with experimental data has been found between the predictions of the model and tests on coupons with different widths.

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Figure 1. Normalised modulus reduction/cycling curves for skin layer specimens at a range of peak stresses. The points are experimental data with the continuous lines fitted through the data at each stress level

Figure 2 Comparison of predicted normalised modulus reduction/cycling curves with experimental data for skin layer specimens at 95, 85 and 75 MPa. The points are experimental data and the continuous lines are the predictions.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram showing an ideal cracked core

Figure 4. Derived crack length in the core versus number of cycles at a peak stress of 70MPa. Each point represents a separate specimen.

Figure 5. Derived crack length in the core versus $(N^{0.3} \sigma^{2.5})$. Each point represents a separate specimen.

Figure 6. Comparison of predicted normalised modulus/cycling curves with experimental data at 80 MPa. The points are experimental data and the continuous lines are predictions.

Figure 7. Normalised modulus/cycling curves for three specimen widths of composite specimens at a peak stress of 70 MPa

Figure 8. Comparison of predicted normalised modulus/cycling curves with experimental data at a peak stress of 70 MPa for 10mm and 30mm wide composite specimens. The points are experimental data and the continuous lines are the predictions